

The Effects of Health Status on Economic Growth in Nigeria:
The Role of Financial Development

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Abstract:

This study examines the relationship between health status and economic growth in Nigeria, while focusing on the moderating role of finance in this relationship. Using annual time series data spanning 1990 to 2022, the study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and the Granger causality test to analyze the short- and long-run effects of health indicators—life expectancy at birth and infant mortality rate on economic growth, while also investigating the moderating influence of financial development. The findings reveal that while improvements in life expectancy positively influence economic growth, this effect is more pronounced in the long run. The findings also revealed that a reduction in infant mortality significantly boosts economic growth in both the short and long run. Furthermore, the results also demonstrate that education plays a critical role in enhancing economic performance, which reinforces the significance of human capital development. However, financial development as a moderating factor yields mixed results. While financial development amplifies the positive impact of life expectancy on economic growth in the short run, its influence is statistically insignificant in the long run. Similarly, financial development does not effectively mitigate the negative impact of high infant mortality on economic growth. This suggests the presence of inefficiencies in financial resource allocation. Hence, these findings underscore the need for sustained investments in health and education alongside financial sector reforms to maximize the economic benefits of improved health outcomes.

Keywords: Health Status, Economic Growth, Financial Development, Life Expectancy, Infant Mortality, Nigeria, ARDL Model.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth, defined as the sustained increase in a country's productive capacity reflected in rising real GDP over time, is influenced by factors such as capital formation, technological advancements, labor expansion, and institutional quality (Jones, 2019). Theories such as the Solow-Swan model and endogenous growth theory highlights the roles of investment, human capital, and innovation as critical drivers of long-term economic performance (Aghion & Howitt, 2021). Empirical evidence further demonstrates that health, education, and infrastructure significantly contribute to economic growth. For instance, bloom et al. (2020) highlight how health improvements enhance labor productivity, while Hanushek and Woessmann (2019) emphasize education's role in fostering technological progress. In developing economies like Nigeria, however, inadequate infrastructure, weak institutions, and low human capital investment often impede growth. Addressing these challenges through policy reforms and strategic investments can improve long-term economic prospects (Ostry et al., 2020). Consequently, sustainable economic growth requires macroeconomic stability, human capital development, and institutional improvements.

Nigeria, Africa's most populous country with over 200 million people, exemplifies these dynamics. Its economy, heavily reliant on oil, has experienced fluctuations, with GDP per capita reaching \$2,163 in 2022 (World Bank Data, 2023). Despite this, health outcomes remain suboptimal, with life expectancy at birth rising from 42.9 years in 1980 to 55.6 years in 2022—still well below the global average of approximately 73 years (World Bank Data, 2023). Between 2000 and 2019, life expectancy averaged around 51 years, significantly lower than the global average of 70 years, while infant mortality rates rank among the world's highest (Awoyemi et al., 2023). These disparities reflect persistent challenges, including maternal and child mortality, rising rates of communicable diseases, and limited access to quality healthcare, particularly in rural areas. Compounding these issues are regional disparities and a dual burden of infectious and non-communicable diseases. Historical trends indicate that while Nigeria's economy has grown—driven by a 4.13% expansion in the non-oil sector in Q2 2024—health improvements have lagged (Ridhwan et al., 2022). A healthier population enhances productivity and economic output, whereas poor health reduces labor productivity and increases costs, hindering development.

The relationship between health status and economic growth has gained widespread recognition, as evidenced by its prominence in the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), where three objectives directly target health and others indirectly support health-enhancing outcomes. Bloom et al. (2018) affirm a positive correlation between sustainable economic growth and health status, a link increasingly vital in resource-constrained nations like Nigeria, where human capital improvement is paramount. However, Nigeria's specific dynamics remain underexplored. The country's heavy dependence on oil revenues introduces volatility, while inadequate investment in

healthcare infrastructure exacerbates health challenges. For instance, Nigeria allocates only 5.03% of its total budget to health—far below the African Union’s recommended 15%—resulting in high out-of-pocket healthcare expenses for citizens (World Health Organization, 2023; African Union, 2001). Given the high opportunity costs of health spending, a compelling rationale is needed to justify increased investment (Onisanwa, 2014).

Financial development plays a pivotal role by enhancing health outcomes and stimulating economic growth in Nigeria. A robust financial system enables greater investment in healthcare infrastructure and services which improves health status and, in turn, labor productivity (Udeh et al., 2021; Ogundipe & Lawal, 2019). Yet, Nigeria’s financial development has been inconsistent, with inadequate credit to the private sector constraining economic progress (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). Strengthening financial systems is thus essential to mobilize resources for health investments, which can amplify economic growth. Existing research often relies on aggregate health indicators, which may fail to capture the multidimensional nature of health in Nigeria, where poverty and inadequate funding further complicate outcomes (Okafor et al., 2024).

Despite Nigeria’s status as Africa’s largest economy, the interplay of health, financial development, and economic growth warrants deeper investigation. This study addresses this gap with three objectives: (1) to examine the effect of health status (life expectancy rate and infant mortality rate) on economic growth in Nigeria, (2) to investigate the existence of causality between health status and economic growth, and (3) to assess the moderating role of finance in the impact of health status on economic growth. This research is significant given Nigeria’s aspirations for sustainable growth. By elucidating the economic benefits of health investments, it can advocate for increased resource allocation to the health sector, particularly in critical areas like maternal and child health, where under-five mortality remains high. Furthermore, the findings can enrich global academic discourse, offering insights from a developing country perspective and refining theoretical models.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Health status and economic growth nexus has been extensively explored by scholars, with various methodologies applied across different regions and time periods. The consensus among scholars suggests that improved health outcomes play a significant role in fostering economic growth, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria.

Abubakar et al. (2024) offer a detailed case for health investment in Nigeria, linking it to economic growth. Using disease burden analysis and economic modeling, they trace Nigeria’s health progress and show that better health boosts productivity and lifespans. They propose a whole-of-government strategy, urging prioritized spending on major diseases and stronger governance to tackle inefficiencies. This comprehensive view introduces the role of finance in health, paving the way for more specific studies.

Onisanwa and Onofowokan (2023) focus on how health spending shapes outcomes and growth. Applying ARDL analysis to 1995-2018 data from the World Bank and Central Bank of Nigeria, they found out that increased expenditure lowers mortality and raises life expectancy, which enhances workforce productivity. Public and private spending showed clear long-run effects on health indicators. They suggest ramping up budgets and using private partnerships.

Ichoku et al. (2021) examine life expectancy's impact on growth, emphasizing poverty's influence. Using FMOLS on 1980-2018 data from the World Bank, they report a 14% growth rise from improved health, with health spending adding 2.8%. A key finding is the 64.4-year life expectancy threshold needed to counter poverty's negative effects. This study ties health financing to poverty reduction and economic gains, extending Onisanwa and Onofowokan's expenditure focus into broader social dynamics.

Lawanson and Ibrahim (2020) explore health's economic role during COVID-19. With ARDL analysis on recent data, they find a 1% life expectancy increase lifts growth by 3.85%, while a 1% death rate rise cuts it by 1.84%. Public spending, however, shows no significant impact, likely due to crisis-related disruptions. This contrasts with Ichoku et al.'s findings in stable times, highlighting how emergencies challenge health financing's effectiveness and demand targeted mortality reduction.

Salisu et al. (2019) investigate how health status drives growth via productivity. Using econometric methods on time-series data, they demonstrate that health investment and financial access together boost labor output significantly, both short- and long-term, fueling economic growth. The study advocates for affordable healthcare and financial inclusion.

Onisanwa (2014) examined whether there is a long-run relationship between health indicators and economic growth in Nigeria. Quarterly time-series data was used, which spanned from 1995 to 2009. Applying cointegration and Granger causality techniques, the study found that health indicators have a positive effect on GDP in the long run. Furthermore, health measures were found to Granger-cause per capita GDP, suggesting that health improvements drive economic expansion over time. The study underscored the importance of enhancing the population's health status to achieve sustained economic growth.

Similarly, Kelani et al. (2019) investigated how health status and labor productivity affects economic growth in Nigeria using annual time-series data from 1981 to 2017. Employing the ARDL bounds testing approach, their findings corroborated Onisanwa's (2014) conclusion, revealing that health status significantly affects economic growth. However, unlike health status, labor productivity didn't exhibit any substantial effect on Nigeria's growth trajectory. The study recommended more investment in education and workforce training in order to enhance labor quality and sustain economic growth.

The relationship that exists between health and the growth of the economy extends beyond Nigeria, as evidenced by Ulman et al. (2017), who documented the critical position of health as a determinant of economic activity in European countries. Their analysis indicated that poor health condition increases the probability of economic inactivity, reinforcing the primacy of health factors over other determinants of economic participation.

Bloom et al. (2018) offered an extensive analysis of the connection between health and economic growth, focusing on three central issues. Initially, they pointed out the difficulties in empirically establishing the direction of causality between health improvements and economic advancement. Next, they observed that the association between health and economic development shifts across distinct phases of economic maturation. Finally, they proposed that various aspects of health—including mortality rates, disease prevalence, child well-being, and the health of older populations—could have diverse impacts on economic outcomes.

Other empirical studies have explored the dynamic interactions between health expenditures, outcomes, and economic growth inclusive. Dormont et al. (2007) made use of pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects models to investigate these relationships and found that health spending triggers technological progress, which, in turn, enhances longevity, quality of life, and labor productivity. They further noted that income growth induces higher health expenditure, as wealthier nations allocate more resources to healthcare.

Kim and Lane (2013) and Jaba et al. (2014) also examined the effects of health spending on national health indicators. Kim and Lane (2013) determined that government health investments are inversely linked to infant mortality rates while showing a positive association with increased life expectancy, highlighting the importance of state-led efforts in enhancing health outcomes. Likewise, Jaba et al. (2014) identified a notable connection between health spending and life expectancy, noting that the magnitude of this effect varies significantly across different countries.

The linkage between health expenditure and economic growth has been explored in the context of emerging markets. Kulkarni (2016) employed panel data regression with fixed effects to analyze the health frameworks of the BRICS nations (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa). The findings indicated a favorable relationship between health outcomes and factors such as GDP per capita, adult literacy levels, and out-of-pocket healthcare costs. Conversely, environmental pollution was shown to adversely impact health conditions, underscoring the critical role of environmental policies in shaping both economic and health strategies.

Several studies have investigated how public health spending shapes health outcomes and economic growth across various regions. Deluna and Peralta (2014) assessed the Philippine economy, revealing that infant mortality decreases as per capita health expenditure and GDP per capita rise. In a similar vein, Day and Tousignant (2005)

evaluated the Canadian economy through vector autoregression (VAR) and impulse response functions, identifying a modest but statistically significant connection between per capita health expenditure, health outcomes, and GDP per capita.

Further supporting evidence comes from Gani (2009), who studied seven Pacific Island countries and found that per capita Government spending on health plays a vital role in shaping health outcomes. Per capita income and immunization rates were also identified as additional factors contributing to better health outcomes, reinforcing the multifaceted nature of the health-economic growth nexus.

3. MODEL SPECIFICATION

This study builds on the framework developed by Adeshina et al. (2019) and Onisanwa (2014), with some adjustments to explore how health status influences economic growth in Nigeria. Health status, serving as the independent variable, is represented by life expectancy at birth (LEB) and infant mortality rate (IMR). Meanwhile, economic growth, the dependent variable, is assessed using gross domestic product per capita (GDP).

Other control variables include:

GCF (growth rate of gross capital formation)

EDU (Education, proxied by secondary school enrollment rate)

LF (Labour force, total)

Hence, the baseline model for this study is given as:

$$GDP_t = a_0 + \beta_1LEB_t + \beta_2GCF_t + \beta_3EDU_t + \beta_4LF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$GDP_t = a_0 + \beta_1IMR_t + \beta_2GCF_t + \beta_3EDU_t + \beta_4LF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

In order to investigate the moderating role of finance in the relationship between health status and economic growth, model (3) and (4) is created. Therefore, we introduced the broad-based financial development index as a proxy for finance, and its interaction with the health status variables (infant mortality rate and life expectancy at birth) in the model.

$$GDP_t = a_0 + \beta_1IMR_t + \beta_2FD_t + \beta_3IMR_FD_t + \beta_4GCF_t + \beta_5EDU_t + \beta_6LF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

$$GDP_t = a_0 + \beta_1LEB_t + \beta_2FD_t + \beta_3LEB_FD_t + \beta_4GCF_t + \beta_5EDU_t + \beta_6LF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Sources of Data

This study employed a quantitative approach to explore the connection between health status and economic growth in Nigeria, while also examining how finance moderates this relationship. It relies on secondary data covering the period from 1995 to 2022. Using time series analysis, the study evaluates yearly secondary data on Nigeria spanning 1990 to 2022. The dataset includes indicators such as life expectancy at birth, infant mortality rate, economic growth, a financial development index, the growth rate of gross capital formation, education levels, and the total labor force. Apart from the broad-based

financial development index that was sourced from International Monetary Fund, all other variable data were drawn from the online version of the World Bank's World Development Indicators Database. These variables are utilized in their raw, untransformed form.

Estimation Techniques

Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Granger Causality Test

The decision to use the ARDL model and the Granger causality test stems from the pre-estimation test outcomes and the nature of the dataset. Unit root tests, specifically the ADF and PP tests, show that the variables include a combination of those stationary at level, $I(0)$, and those requiring first differencing, $I(1)$. This mix suits the ARDL model's strength in accommodating variables with varying integration orders, as highlighted by Pesaran and Shin (1999). Moreover, the ARDL Bounds test reveals a long-term link between health status and economic growth, with the F-statistic surpassing the critical threshold at the 5% significance level. This finding supports the use of the ARDL model to capture both short-term fluctuations and long-term equilibrium relationships. Additionally, the Granger causality test plays a key role in determining the causal direction between health status—measured through life expectancy and infant mortality rate—and economic growth, assessing whether shifts in health indicators drive economic changes or the reverse. This method ensures a dynamic analysis over time and strengthens the reliability of the findings, consistent with econometric standards. Previous research, such as Narayan (2005) and Pesaran et al. (2001), endorses the ARDL approach for datasets with mixed integration levels and cointegrated variables, while Granger (1969) lays the groundwork for causality analysis. Together, these techniques provide a thorough insight into the relationship between health status and economic growth in Nigeria.

The specific ARDL form of the models used in this study is given:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GDP_t = & a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \Delta IMR_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \eta_k \Delta GCF_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \theta_k \Delta EDU_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \lambda_k \Delta LF_{t-k} \\ & + a_1 GDP_{t-1} + a_2 IMR_{t-1} + a_3 GCF_{t-1} + a_4 EDU_{t-1} + a_5 LF_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GDP_t = & a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \Delta LEB_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \eta_k \Delta GCF_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \theta_k \Delta EDU_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \lambda_k \Delta LF_{t-k} \\ & + a_1 GDP_{t-1} + a_2 IMR_{t-1} + a_3 GCF_{t-1} + a_4 EDU_{t-1} + a_5 LF_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GDP_t = & a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \Delta IMR_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \eta_k \Delta FD_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \theta_k \Delta IMR_FD_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \lambda_k \Delta GCF_{t-k} \\ & + \sum_{k=0}^p \partial_k \Delta EDU_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \delta_k \Delta LF_{t-k} + a_1 GDP_{t-1} + a_2 IMR_{t-1} + a_3 FD_{t-1} \\ & + a_4 IMR_FD_{t-1} + a_5 GCF_{t-1} + a_6 EDU_{t-1} + a_7 LF_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

(7)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GDP_t = & a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^n \gamma_k \Delta LEB_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \eta_k \Delta FD_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \theta_k \Delta LEB_FD_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \lambda_k \Delta GCF_{t-k} \\ & + \sum_{k=0}^p \partial_k \Delta EDU_{t-k} + \sum_{k=0}^p \delta_k \Delta LF_{t-k} + a_1 GDP_{t-1} + a_2 IMR_{t-1} + a_3 FD_{t-1} \\ & + a_4 IMR_FD_{t-1} + a_5 GCF_{t-1} + a_6 EDU_{t-1} + a_7 LF_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

(8)

The Granger (1969) approach allows us to evaluate how current GDP is shaped by its own past values and then determine if including lagged values of an explanatory variable enhances this understanding. We consider that GDP Granger-causes the explanatory variable, x, if x contributes to predicting GDP more effectively. To explore this, we will conduct bivariate regression analyses structured as follows.

$$y_t = \sum_{i=1}^k a_i x_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (4)$$

$$x_t = \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_i x_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \rho_i y_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad (5)$$

Where ϵ_t and μ_t are two white noise series and k is maximum number of lags

Summary Statistics

Table 1 descriptive statistics reveal important details into the dataset. The dependent variable GDP has an average of 1956.06 with moderate variability (standard deviation of 443.64), ranging from 1390.47 to 2585.73. Infant mortality rate (IMR) averages 96.26 deaths per 1,000 live births, showing considerable variability (standard deviation of 18.99) and a decline from 124.4 to 68.5. Life expectancy at birth (LEB) averages 49.28 years, with a relatively small variation (standard deviation of 2.79), ranging from 45.49 to 53.63 years. Financial development (FD) shows an average of 0.194219, while a low variability of 0.035383 as seen in the standard deviation. Gross capital formation (GCF) exhibits high variability (standard deviation of 12.05), reflecting both negative and substantial positive investment rates. Education (EDU), measured by secondary school enrollment, averages 35.15% with variability (standard deviation of 9.36), while the labor force (LF) shows substantial size and variability, averaging over 52 million with a standard deviation of 12.76 million. These statistics provide a comprehensive overview of Nigeria's socioeconomic dynamics over the sampled period.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	IMR	LEB	FD	GCF	EDU	LF
Mean	1956.060	96.26364	49.28133	0.194219	2.286667	35.15107	52140844
Median	1949.159	92.10000	49.73000	0.198753	3.250000	34.85191	50928728
Maximum	2585.734	124.4000	53.63300	0.272725	40.74000	54.88297	76374344
Minimum	1390.469	68.50000	45.48700	0.123073	- 22.79000	23.54534	33185856
Std. Dev.	443.6351	18.98708	2.791450	0.035383	12.05452	9.363605	12763138
Observations	33	33	33	33	33	33	32

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

Unit Root Test

Table 2 displays the outcomes of the unit root tests performed to check the stationarity of the time series and their integration levels. Using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron tests, the findings indicate that, aside from gross capital formation, which is stationary at its level form, all other variables achieve stationarity only after first differencing. This combination of integration orders suggests that some estimation methods are unsuitable for analyzing the specified model. Given this, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach stands out as the most fitting linear regression technique. However, before proceeding, the ARDL bounds test for cointegration will be carried out to confirm whether a long-term relationship exists among the variables.

Table 2. Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philips-perron Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF		PP		Conclusion
	Statistics	Prob.	Statistics	Prob.	
GDP	-2.956021	0.0505	-2.932559	0.0530	I (1)
LEB	-3.648048	0.0103	-3.648048	0.0103	I (1)
IMR	-4.485710	0.0014	-1.902609	0.0556	I (1)
FD	-5.357563	0.0001	-5.637637	0.0001	I (1)
EDU	-8.110744	0.0000	-8.210086	0.0000	I (1)
LF	-4.314236	0.0022	-6.736761	0.0000	I (1)
GCF	-9.944179	0.0000	-10.83943	0.0000	I (0)

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

Co-integration analysis

The results of the ARDL bounds test across all models, from Model 1 to Model 4, reveal the existence of long-term relationships among the variables. For each model, the F-statistic—recorded as 9.38 for Model 1, 11.02 for Model 2, 11.4 for Model 3, and 6.9 for

Model 4 which surpasses the upper critical value (I1 Bound) at the 5% significance level. This outcome allows us to reject the null hypothesis that no long-run relationships exist. These results indicate that the independent variables in each model are cointegrated with the dependent variable, pointing to a consistent long-term equilibrium connection among the variables throughout the study period.

Table 3. ARDL Bounds Test

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist							
Model	Sample	Included Obs	Test Statistic (F-statistic)	k	Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
Model 1	1992–2022	31	9.377465	4	10%	2.45	3.52
					5%	2.86	4.01
Model 2	1992–2022	31	11.02288	4	10%	2.45	3.52
					5%	2.86	4.01
Model 3	1992–2022	31	11.36902	6	10%	2.12	3.23
					5%	2.45	3.61
Model 4	1992–2022	31	6.886896	6	10%	2.12	3.23
					5%	2.45	3.61

Source: Authors’ Computation using EViews 8

The Effects of Health Status (Life Expectancy at Birth) on Economic Growth Short Run Dynamics

As shown in Table 6, the short-run results indicate that shifts in life expectancy (D(LEB)) positively influence economic growth, though this effect lacks statistical significance. This observation aligns with Bloom et al. (2018), who noted that the link between health and economic growth is intricate, with the benefits of improved health often emerging only after some delay. The lack of immediate significance in these health improvements suggests that the boost to productivity from better health needs time to fully reflect in economic outcomes. Similarly, Deluna and Peralta (2014) found that short-term fluctuations in health indicators may not immediately translate into significant economic growth, which calls for a sustained investment in health systems.

The findings also reveal that gross capital formation (D(GCF)) positively affects GDP growth in the short run, but this impact is not statistically significant. This echoes Kelani et al. (2019), who observed that while health status plays a notable role in economic growth, labor productivity tends to lack a meaningful effect during short-term growth periods in Nigeria. Additionally, the short-run results show that changes in the labor force (D(LF)) positively and significantly boost economic growth, which aligns with Dormont et al. (2007). They argued that a healthier workforce lifts productivity and participation rates, though these benefits often unfold over time.

Another important insight from the short-run analysis is the positive and statistically significant influence of education (D(EDU)) on economic growth. This highlights the vital role of human capital development in spurring economic activity, even in the near term. This finding is in line with Jaba et al. (2014), who identified a clear connection between education and economic progress, and Kim and Lane (2013), who stressed the value of public health spending in strengthening human capital. Furthermore, the presence of a significant and negative error correction term (CointEq(-1)) points to a robust mechanism for returning to long-run equilibrium. Specifically, it suggests that any short-term drift from this balance is corrected at a speed rate of 40%.

Long-Run Relationships

In the long run, life expectancy at birth (LEB) exhibits a highly significant and positive effect on economic growth, which indicates that improved health outcomes contribute meaningfully to sustained economic growth. The ARDL results show a coefficient of 270.99 which means that a one-year increase in life expectancy pumps GDP per capita up by approximately 271 units. This corroborates the work of Onisanwa (2014), who found that health indicators have a long-run impact on economic growth in Nigeria and that higher life expectancy enhances per capita GDP. The findings also align with Ulman et al. (2017), who documented that poor health status negatively impacts labor participation and economic activity in European countries, further emphasizing the universal relevance of health investments.

The positive, however statistically insignificant, coefficient for gross capital formation (GCF) in the long run suggests that while investment remains crucial, its direct influence on GDP growth may be contingent on other structural factors. This echoes Dormont et al. (2007), who identified that health spending indirectly boosts economic growth by improving human capital and increasing labor force productivity.

Notably, the labor force (LF) shows a statistically significant yet negative link to economic growth over the long term. This implies that simply increasing the labor force might not lead to economic benefits unless it is matched by sufficient job opportunities and improvements in productivity. This is consistent with findings from Kulkarni (2016), who examined BRICS economies and found that demographic factors, when unaccompanied by economic opportunities, can lead to diminishing returns on growth.

Finally, the positive long-term effect of education (EDU) on economic growth reinforces the critical importance of human capital development, a pattern echoed in earlier

research like Kelani et al. (2019) and Gani (2009). The result shows that a unit increase in the number of people enrolled in school adds 24.03 units in the productivity level of people in Nigeria, hence increases overall economic growth. The results reinforce the argument that sustained improvements in education contribute to skill development, innovation, and economic resilience, ultimately fostering long-term growth.

Table 4. ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form

Dependent Variable: GDP				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 1, 0, 1, 1)				
Short Run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LEB)	51.532937	32.001926	1.610307	0.1216
D(GCF)	0.495612	0.625804	0.791962	0.4368
D(LF)	0.000073	0.000041	1.790975	0.0871
D(EDU)	5.962710	2.452733	2.431047	0.0237
CointEq(-1)	-0.401176	0.082602	-4.856758	0.0001
Cointeq = GDP - (270.9851*LEB + 1.2354*GCF -0.0000*LF + 24.0273				
*EDU -10042.9964)				
Long Run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LEB	270.985148	51.125871	5.300353	0.0000
GCF	1.235400	1.609677	0.767483	0.4510
LF	-0.000047	0.000012	-3.939204	0.0007
EDU	24.027350	6.806914	3.529845	0.0019
C	-10042.99637	1944.653084	-5.164415	0.0000

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

The Effects of Health Status (Infant Mortality Rate) on Economic Growth Short-Run Dynamics

Table 7 displays the ARDL regression outcomes exploring how the infant mortality rate affects economic growth. In the short term, shifts in the infant mortality rate (D(IMR)) show a statistically significant and negative influence on economic growth. With a coefficient of -11.66, the results suggest that reducing IMR by one unit sparks a substantial rise in GDP, highlighting the immediate and powerful boost that better child health can give to economic outcomes. This observation is consistent with Deluna and Peralta (2014), who noted a clear negative link between infant mortality rates and GDP per capita. Gross capital formation (D(GCF)) displays a positive association with GDP in the short run; however, this relationship lacks statistical significance. This suggests that short-term fluctuations in investment levels may not directly translate into immediate economic

benefits, a result that is consistent with Kelani et al. (2019), who found that labor productivity and capital formation had limited short-term impacts on economic growth in Nigeria.

Labor force changes (D(LF)) show a positive and marginally significant effect, implying that increases in the labor force can moderately influence short-run economic outcomes. This finding supports Dormont et al. (2007), who identified labor force participation as a crucial channel through which health influences economic growth.

Education (D(EDU)), measured by secondary school enrollment, reveals a positive and statistically significant influence on GDP in the short run. This finding highlights the immediate value of education in enhancing economic activity by improving workforce capabilities, productivity, and innovation—a perspective reinforced by Kelani et al. (2019) and Jaba et al. (2014).

The error correction term (CointEq(-1)) is both statistically significant and negative, with a coefficient of -0.216. This suggests that approximately 22% of any divergence from the long-run equilibrium is adjusted each year, indicating a moderately paced return to equilibrium.

Long-Run Relationships

Over the long term, the infant mortality rate (IMR) exhibits a statistically significant and negative association with economic growth, reflected by a coefficient of -53.92. This implies that a one-unit decrease in IMR is associated with a substantial increase in GDP per capita by 53.92 units. The result highlights the profound long-term benefits of improving health outcomes, particularly reducing child mortality, in fostering sustained economic development. This finding corroborates those of Gani (2009) and Kim and Lane (2013), who found strong evidence that improved health indicators enhance economic performance.

Gross capital formation (GCF) displays a positive coefficient in the long run, though it lacks statistical significance. This observation corresponds with Kelani et al. (2019), who argued that investment by itself does not ensure economic growth unless supported by additional elements, such as human capital development and institutional quality.

Labor force (LF) shows a statistically significant and negative relationship with GDP in the long run. This suggests that labor force expansion without corresponding productivity growth or adequate economic opportunities may strain resources and hinder per capita GDP growth. This result aligns with the concerns raised by Dormont et al. (2007) regarding the need for productivity-enhancing policies to optimize labor contributions to economic growth.

Education (EDU) manifests a statistically significant and positive long-term influence on GDP, evidenced by a coefficient of 31.36. This result underscores the pivotal contribution of human capital development to sustaining long-term economic progress. Enhanced educational attainment fosters a proficient workforce equipped to promote innovation and bolster economic expansion, a perspective corroborated by Kelani et al. (2019) and Jaba et al. (2014).

Table 5. ARDL Cointegrating and Long Run Form

Dependent Variable: GDP				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 0, 0, 1, 0)				
Short run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IMR)	-11.660760	1.799571	-6.479745	0.0000
D(GCF)	0.719565	0.559008	1.287219	0.2103
D(LF)	0.000069	0.000038	1.808651	0.0831
D(EDU)	6.782065	2.259528	3.001541	0.0062
CointEq(-1)	-0.216266	0.054049	-4.001286	0.0005
Cointeq = GDP2 - (-53.9187*IMR + 3.3272*GCF -0.0001*LF + 31.3599				
*EDU + 9459.9475)				
Long Run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IMR	-53.918697	14.968901	-3.602048	0.0014
GCF	3.327230	2.672099	1.245174	0.2251
LF	-0.000075	0.000027	-2.823819	0.0094
EDU	31.359886	8.861956	3.538710	0.0017
C	9459.94749	2561.220079	3.693532	0.0011

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

The moderating Role of Finance in the Health Status and Economic growth Nexus

Examining the individual and moderating effect of finance on economic growth shows that in the short-run results presented in Tables 6, financial development (FD) appears to have an insignificant impact on economic growth, which may reflect inefficiencies in financial resource allocation or weak institutional mechanisms for channeling funds effectively. The interaction term (IMR_FD) is positive but statistically insignificant in the short run, implying that financial development does not immediately mitigate the adverse impact of infant mortality rate (IMR) on economic growth. In the long run, this interaction turns negative but remains insignificant, suggesting that financial development has not played a meaningful role in counteracting the detrimental effects of high infant mortality on economic growth. These results are consistent with Lawanson and Ibrahim (2020), who found that while public health spending positively influences economic growth, its effects are often neutralized during periods of economic instability, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, Bloom et al. (2018) emphasized that financial resources alone are insufficient to drive sustained improvements in health and

economic outcomes. Education (EDU) significantly boosts economic growth in both the short and long run, underscoring the importance of human capital investments.

As seen in the result presented in Table 7, Financial development (FD) exhibits a significant positive effect on economic growth in the short run, but remains statistically insignificant in the long run, suggesting that short-term financial inflows stimulate economic activity, but structural inefficiencies limit its long-term effectiveness. These findings resonate with Ichoku et al. (2021), who reported a 14% growth increase attributed to improved health, alongside a 2.8% contribution from health spending.

Their study further demonstrated the importance of surpassing a life expectancy threshold to mitigate poverty's negative economic effects. Furthermore, the interaction between LEB and FD (LEB_FD) is positive and significant in the short run with a probability value of 0.0374, indicating that financial development amplifies the benefits of increased life expectancy on economic growth in the immediate term. However, this effect is insignificant in the long run, implying that financial development fails to consistently enhance the long-term growth benefits of improved life expectancy. This aligns with Salisu et al. (2019), who emphasized the necessity of integrating health investment with financial accessibility to maximize labor productivity and economic growth. Moreover, studies such as Kim and Lane (2013) and Jaba et al. (2014) demonstrated that public health expenditures significantly improve life expectancy and reduce infant mortality, but their effectiveness depends on efficient financial management and governance.

Table 6. ARDL Cointegrating and Long Run Form

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form				
Dependent Variable: GDP				
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1)				
Sample: 1990 2022				
Included observations: 31				
Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IMR)	-11.950449	3.689040	-3.239447	0.0043
D(FD)	-4495.625685	3184.478434	-1.411731	0.1742
D(IMR_FD)	52.469547	33.388592	1.571481	0.1326
D(GCF)	0.471445	0.555278	0.849026	0.4064
D(LF)	0.000046	0.000037	1.246516	0.2277
D(EDU)	5.612539	2.250026	2.494433	0.0220
CointEq(-1)	-0.365746	0.079363	-4.608551	0.0002
Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IMR	-32.674141	13.976583	-2.337777	0.0305
FD	5412.970008	6014.965143	0.899917	0.3794
IMR_FD	-50.460542	63.169520	-0.798812	0.4343

GCF	1.288995	1.580562	0.815530	0.4249
LF	-0.000049	0.000013	-3.777353	0.0013
EDU	26.432157	6.789197	3.893267	0.0010
C	6443.633335	1893.823158	3.402447	0.0030

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

Table 7. ARDL Cointegrating and Long Run Form

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form				
Dependent Variable: GDP				
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1)				
Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LEB)	115.691869	27.469130	4.211705	0.0005
D(FD)	22529.481888	9692.623045	2.324395	0.0313
D(LEB_FD)	443.004948	197.954844	2.237909	0.0374
D(GCF)	0.482721	0.548902	0.879430	0.3902
D(LF)	0.000086	0.000036	2.406629	0.0264
D(EDU)	5.960919	2.221707	2.683036	0.0147
CointEq(-1)	-0.415321	0.080655	-5.149382	0.0001
Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LEB	278.559990	90.882971	3.065041	0.0064
FD	9962.471283	19050.326519	0.522955	0.6071
LEB_FD	-168.578963	387.720524	-0.434795	0.6686
GCF	1.162284	1.370233	0.848238	0.4069
LF	-0.000046	0.000010	-4.568331	0.0002
EDU	25.823943	5.949144	4.340783	0.0004
C	-	4158.609333	-2.619514	0.0169
	10893.534204			

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

Granger Causality Test

The Granger causality test outcomes presented in Table 8 demonstrate a bidirectional causal relationship between the infant mortality rate (IMR) and GDP per capita (GDP). This suggests a reciprocal dynamic wherein variations in IMR can forecast subsequent shifts in economic growth, and changes in economic growth can likewise predict alterations in IMR. Correspondingly, a two-way causal link exists between life expectancy at birth (LEB) and GDP, indicating that increases in life expectancy may stimulate economic growth, while economic advancements also support improvements in life expectancy through enhanced healthcare and living conditions. Additionally, IMR

Granger causes LEB, highlighting that reductions in infant mortality contribute to increases in overall life expectancy, while the reverse relationship is not significant. These findings show the interrelationship between health indicators and economic performance, which emphasizes the importance of integrated health and economic policies for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Table 8. Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Sample: 1990 2022			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
IMR does not Granger Cause GDP	31	3.95068	0.0318
GDP does not Granger Cause IMR		8.14347	0.0018
LEB does not Granger Cause GDP	31	3.77429	0.0364
GDP does not Granger Cause LEB		4.74719	0.0175
LEB does not Granger Cause IMR	31	0.98772	0.3860
IMR does not Granger Cause LEB		14.6464	5.E-05

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 8

Diagnostic Test

The study employs several diagnostic tests, as revealed in Table 10, to check for the efficiency, accuracy, reliability, and stability of the models under the linear ARDL approach. R- and adjusted R-squared are employed in evaluating the fitness of the linear and non-linear ARDL models. This study employs several diagnostic tests to assess the robustness of the ARDL models. The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test is conducted to evaluate whether the residuals exhibit homoscedasticity, the Durbin-Watson test is used to examine the presence of serial correlation in the residuals, the normality test assesses the distributional properties of the variables, and the cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) tests are applied to verify the stability of the long-run coefficients in the ARDL models. As reported in Table 9, the R-squared and adjusted R-squared values indicate that the exogenous variables—namely life expectancy at birth, infant mortality rate, financial development index, gross capital formation, labor force, and education—collectively explain approximately 99% and 99%, respectively, of the variation in economic growth across all models. The F-statistics, with values of 498, 717, 475.1323, and 484.6071 for the four models, are statistically significant, confirming that the independent variables jointly exert a substantial influence. The Durbin-Watson statistics suggest no evidence of autocorrelation, indicating that the residuals in each model are independent of one another. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera test yields insignificant results, supporting the conclusion that the variables follow a normal distribution. Lastly, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test produces insignificant F-statistics of 1.052679, 0.963752, 0.966792, and 0.973960 for ARDL Models 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively, demonstrating that the residuals are homoscedastic and thus consistent across the range of exogenous variable values.

The CUSUM and CUSUMSQ plots in Figures 1 to 4 reveal that the long-run coefficients are stable since both of their plots stay inside the critical bounds. In other words, the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ plots support the long-run impacts of life expectancy at birth and infant mortality rate on economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 9 Diagnostic Test

Test	ARDL Model 1	ARDL Model 2	ARDL Model 3	ARDL Model 4
R-squared	0.994510	0.994455	0.996378	0.996448
Adjusted R-squared	0.992514	0.993069	0.994281	0.994392
F-statistic (p-value)	498.2061 (0.00000)	717.3687 (0.00000)	475.1323 (0.00000)	484.6071 (0.00000)
Durbin-Watson	1.536045	1.71121	1.660503	1.58487
Jarque-Bera (p-value)	0.732578 (0.693302)	2.697624 (0.259548)	2.217889 (0.329907)	0.893630 (0.639662)
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	1.052679 (0.4292)	0.963752 (0.4702)	0.966792 (0.5055)	0.973960 (0.5001)

Source: Authors' Construction using EViews 8

Model 1

Figure 1. CUSUM and CUSUM Squared

Model 2

Figure 2. CUSUM and CUSUM Squared

Model 3

Figure 3. CUSUM and CUSUM Squared

Model 4

Figure 4. CUSUM and CUSUM Squared

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This research highlights the essential influence of health on Nigeria’s economic growth, demonstrating that although short-term advancements in health metrics, such as life expectancy and infant mortality, may not promptly result in economic gains, their long-term effects are considerable. The findings show that higher life expectancy significantly boosts economic growth, reinforcing the idea that a healthier population leads to a more productive workforce and sustained economic development. Conversely, high infant mortality rates negatively affect economic performance, highlighting the urgent need for targeted interventions to improve child health outcomes. Furthermore, while financial development shows a positive effect on economic growth in the short run, its long-run impact remains statistically insignificant, which mirrors inefficiencies in financial resource allocation. Moreover, the interaction between financial development and infant mortality fails to mitigate the adverse effects of poor health on growth, while financial development enhances the short-term benefits of life expectancy but lacks a sustained long-term impact.

The bidirectional causality between health and economic growth suggests that improvements in health not only drive economic prosperity but that economic growth also facilitates better health outcomes through increased access to healthcare services, improved living conditions, and higher public health expenditures. These findings emphasize that health investments should not be viewed merely as social spending but as a critical driver of economic progress.

Given these findings, the Nigerian government should prioritize sustained investment in healthcare infrastructure, maternal and child health services, disease prevention programs to ensure long-term economic benefits and strengthen financial institutions to better support health investments. Strengthening financial institutions and healthcare policies, increasing budgetary allocations to the health sector, and enhancing access to quality medical care—particularly in rural and underserved areas—will be essential in improving life expectancy and reducing infant mortality rates. Furthermore, investment

in human capital through education should complement health initiatives, as the study finds that education significantly contributes to economic growth in both the short and long run. A skilled and healthy workforce is necessary to harness the economic advantages of improved health status. Additionally, labor market reforms that create employment opportunities and enhance productivity will help translate a growing labor force into tangible economic gains. In light of these findings, an integrated policy approach that aligns health, education, and economic strategies is crucial for Nigeria to achieve sustained economic growth and development.

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